

Data-driven models for a salt production process towards an Industry 4.0 evolution ^{*}

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Abstract: This work develops a predictive model of the production process of brine salt in an Italian industrial site. The methodology uses dimensionality reduction via standard statistical techniques and one year of production data has been acquired via direct connection to the plant control system. A code developed in Python analyze each plant, screen the raw data, and regress the models via principal component regression (PCR) and partial least squares (PLS). Results show good reliability for the prediction of the evaporative plant while the depuration model still needs refinements to be performed.

Keywords: Modeling, Industry 4.0, PCA, Brine Salt Production, Data-Driven

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition to the Industry 4.0 paradigm requires developing models of production processes (Krishnamurthi and Kumar, 2020). Different modeling techniques have been explored in this sense. First principle mechanistic modeling are widely employed (e.g. Vaccari et al. (2021)) while process simulation aid companies to evaluate the roadmap toward Industry 4.0 (de Paula Ferreira et al., 2020). The computational costs of rigorous simulation models have also been overcome with machine learning methodologies to develop appropriate surrogate models (Muhsin and Zhang, 2022). On the other hand, data-driven models are often considered black-box solutions that require engineering knowledge for application to process systems (Bikmukhametov and Jäschke, 2020); for this reason, dimensionality of chosen models and the quality and quantity of data to be treated by algorithms becomes important factors in this analysis (Khayyam et al., 2020). Also, system identification is used to build data-driven dynamic models for which data quality has to be carefully checked (Shardt et al., 2020). In this context, input-output static models can be a first step in the analysis of a process and understanding of its criticalities at a low computational cost. For this reason their development for a brine salt production process is analyzed in this paper. Data-driven models are here preferred over first-principles ones due to the high level of interactions and complex chemical equilibrium at the base of product impurities removal. This work is part of a larger competitive project that aims to bring technological innovations to an Italian industrial site, in line with the Industry 4.0 paradigm, to improve process efficiency and safety.

2. PLANT DESCRIPTION

This study aims to develop a predictive model for the production process of brine salt of Locatelli Saline di Volterra SPA. A process flow diagram (PFD) of the production process is shown in Figure 1. First, the preheated raw brine enters the purification plant: four parallel stirred reactors in which the main impurities (calcium and magnesium ions), are abated by feeding calcium oxide (CaO), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), and the recycled concentrated brine from the evaporative section. CaO maintains the solution pH and ensure the correct precipitation of impurities, thus the purity of the resulting brine; Na₂CO₃ is used to insert the carbonate ions that, together with sulfate ions in the recirculated brine, modify the complex solubility equilibrium in the reactors. The pH of the reactor is measured at two points: the top of the reactor where the purified brine overflows and above the insertion of the heated raw brine. Samples are collected at spot and analyzed offline in test laboratories. Insoluble materials are extracted from the bottom as liquid slag and sent to landfill as solid residues. Next, the purified brine enters the evaporation plant: three parallel vertical evaporators maintained at constant pressure by four turbochargers. The brine is fed into the evaporator and circulated into an external heat exchanger to reach the evaporative temperature. The evaporated steam is ducted, treated in a scrubber, condensed, and sent back to the preheater zone to recover some waste heat. Additional brine is removed in a mixer by centrifugation and recirculated back to the evaporators, while the concentrated stream is treated in a drying plant to produce salt. Indeed, processes for removing impurities in raw brine must be properly operated to ensure the purified brine meets quality limits imposed by the market and the final product. Hence, purification and evaporation of the purified brine are the phases analyzed in this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

A process block diagram, comprising the four phases that the brine undergoes (pre-heating, depuration, concentration by

^{*} This research was funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement number 101079342 (Fostering Opportunities Towards Slovak Excellence in Advanced Control for Smart Industries).

Fig. 1. Simplified PFD of Locatelli process; plants analyzed are highlighted, bold lines trace path from raw brine to final product.

Table 1. Inputs and Outputs analyzed for the two plants. Parameters with “*” are shared among all the reactors/evaporators in the plant.

Plant	Symbol	Parameter	Unit
Brine Depuration	IN1R*	T inlet brine	°C
	IN2R	F raw heated brine	m ³ /h
	IN3R	F CaO	Hz
	IN4R	F Na ₂ CO ₃	L/h
	OUT1R	pH at above brine inlet	-
	OUT2R	pH at reactor outlet	-
	OUT3R	CaCO ₃ concentration in the reactor	g/L
	OUT4R	MgOH ₂ concentration in the reactor	g/L
	OUT5R	Purified brine appearance	-
	Brine Concentration by evaporation	IN1EV*	T inlet brine
IN2EV		F purified brine	m ³ /h
IN3EV		F brine from mixer	m ³ /h
OUT1EV*		Electric absorption of turbochargers	A
OUT2EV*		P evaporators head	barA
OUT3EV		Evaporators level	%
OUT4EV		ΔT heat exchangers	°C

evaporation, drying and packing), is firstly developed to better identify the input-output relationships between the various parameters affecting the operations. The input and output parameters for the two blocks under study are listed in Table 1. Production data histories are acquired via connection to the facility DCS. The extracted data trends are continuous but most of the real measurements are sampled with time steps greater than the ones chosen, therefore they are automatically reformulated as the average in the interval between two successive samplings. Moreover, to collect and analyze the process data, a specific code has been developed in Python. The object-oriented tool Python “Class” has been used to group variables and operations common to multiple data sets, creating a flexible and compact code applicable to all parsing blocks (see Figure 2).

Data Screening. As anticipated in Section 1, data quality is very important in data-driven models. Hence, few screening criteria are applied to the N original samples collected. The production data sampled with 1 hour time step contains different values not applicable to the analysis, e.g. values labeled as *not available*. Moreover, the data commonly known as “outliers” in statistical analysis are also eliminated, i.e. those data that do not fall within the range of three standard deviations with respect to the average value of the considered parameter. As a

Fig. 2. Flux of operations for the data analysis and model development of one block as described in Section 3.

last screening criterion, samplings with a null value are deleted in those parameters for which a null sampling corresponds to invalid data, as indicated by Locatelli, i.e. a zero brine flow rate value to the purification block. Conversely, zero values are preserved in the model for parameters in which a null value is considered physically valid, i.e. a zero concentration of hydrates in the reactors can indicate their complete neutralization.

Check data parallelization. The two plants studied in the Locatelli facility are composed of four reactors and three evaporators, but it is important to study how much these “sub-blocks” can be considered parallel operations before applying regression functions. Each block analyzed has n_y outputs and n_x inputs; most of them are related to all the unit operations in the plants, e.g. the j th input of the evaporators can be represented as $x_j = [x_j^1, x_j^2, x_j^3]$, while others are shared among all the block units (marked with “*” in Table 1). Therefore, after removing nonnumeric values, each i th output and j th input are analyzed using the principal component analysis (PCA) to check if the behavior of each sub-block with respect to each variable is

Algorithm 1 General data screening procedure for each y_i^b

- 1: Screen $x_{j,i}^b \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$
- 2: Store the samples indices to be excluded $z = [z_1, \dots, z_{n_z}]$
- 3: Remove the n_z samples related to z from y_i^b and $x_{j,i}^b$

$$y_i^{b'} = y_i^b[0 : N - n_z] \leftarrow y_i^b[0 : N] - z$$

$$x_{j,i}^{b'} = x_{j,i}^b[0 : N - n_z] \leftarrow x_{j,i}^b[0 : N] - z \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$$

- 4: Screen the updated output dataset $y_i^{b'}$
- 5: Store the samples indices to be excluded $w = [w_1, \dots, w_{n_w}]$
- 6: Remove the n_w samples related to w from $y_i^{b'}$ and $x_{j,i}^{b'}$

$$y_i^{b''} = y_i^{b'}[0 : n_s] \leftarrow y_i^{b'}[0 : N - n_z] - w$$

$$x_{j,i}^{b''} = x_{j,i}^{b'}[0 : n_s] \leftarrow x_{j,i}^{b'}[0 : N - n_z] - w \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$$

$$n_s = N - n_z - n_w$$

- 7: Extract $y_i^{b''}$ and $x_{j,i}^{b''} \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$ to be sent to regression
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uniform to the others or if it needs to be studied as independent. The number of sub-blocks related to the i th output (n_{b,y_i}) or j th input (n_{b,x_j}) corresponds to the main components from the PCA with an explained variance (EV) above the threshold limit chosen (λ_{PCA}). Performing these operations for all n_y outputs and n_x inputs, the number of sub-blocks chosen as representative for further analysis of the block is the maximum one, as follows:

$$n_b = \max[n_{b,x_1}, \dots, n_{b,x_j}, \dots, n_{b,x_{n_x}}, n_{b,y_1}, \dots, n_{b,y_i}, \dots, n_{b,y_{n_y}}] \quad (1)$$

Parallelization is not studied for parameters common to all sub-blocks, e.g. the temperature of the reactors/evaporators inlet streams, as such variables are not distributed among them.

Model regression via MISO approach. Once evaluating the number n_b in which the block can be modeled, the regression is structured according to the Multiple Input Single Output (MISO) approach. We aim to find relationships between the individual outputs $y_i^b \forall b = 1, \dots, n_b \wedge i = 1, \dots, n_y$ and their related inputs $x_{j,i}^b \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$. Correlations among different outputs in a block are ignored. For each output y_i^b the general data screening procedure is performed as listed in Algorithm 1. These steps are needed to maintain dimensional consistency between the various inputs and their respective outputs. The statistical methods used to regress $y_i^{b''}$ with $x_{j,i}^{b''} \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$ are two: the principal component regression (PCR) and the partial least squares (PLS) (Mejdell and Skogestad, 1991). The number of main components considered is calculated through a percentage increase of the EV, with the threshold value set to 5%. Starting from the second one, each principal component EV is added to the previous cumulative value only if this increase is larger than 5%, increasing the number of principal components considered. For reference, all the statistical functions used (PCA, PCR and PLS) are taken from the `scikit-learn` package (Pedregosa et al., 2011). Finally, the i th output prediction is built by Eq. (2):

$$\hat{y}_i^b[k] = a_{0,i} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_x} \frac{a_{j,i}(x_{j,i}^b[k - \theta] - \bar{x}_{j,i}^b)}{\sigma_{x_{j,i}^b}} \quad (2)$$

in which $\hat{y}_i^b[k]$ is the value estimated by the model at time k for the input $x_{j,i}^b[k - \theta] \forall j = 1, \dots, n_x$ at time $k - \theta$, while $a_{0,i}$ and $a_{j,i}$ are the constant calculated by the regression functions, and $\bar{x}_{j,i}^b$ and $\sigma_{x_{j,i}^b}$ are mean value and standard deviation of $x_{j,i}^b$. For an easier model deployment, the code returns constants $\kappa_{0,i}$ and $\kappa_{j,i}$ used to calculate the predictive model as in Eq. (3):

$$\hat{y}_i^b[k] = \kappa_{0,i} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_x} \kappa_{j,i} x_{j,i}^b[k - \theta] \quad (3)$$

where $\kappa_{0,i} = a_{0,i} - \sum_{j=1}^{n_x} (a_{j,i} \bar{x}_{j,i}^b / \sigma_{x_{j,i}^b})$ and $\kappa_{j,i} = a_{j,i} / \sigma_{x_{j,i}^b}$.

Model reliability evaluation. To quantify the prediction accuracy, the root mean square error (RMSE) is adopted as it is frequently used in statistical analyses to represent a global error estimate for predicting a parameter. It is calculated via Eq. (4):

$$RMSE_y = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} (\hat{y}_i^b[k] - y_i^b[k])^2}{n_s}} \quad (4)$$

where $y_i^b[k]$ is the observed sample value at time k and n_s the number of samples considered by the model, i.e. those after data screening in Algorithm 1, i.e. $n_s < N$. Even if a small RMSE value is always preferable, it cannot be used as the only evaluation criterion for the prediction effectiveness of all parameters as it depends on the scale of values used. To eliminate this dependence, a normalization is carried out with respect to the average value of the analyzed output \bar{y}_i^b , defining $NRMSE_y = RMSE_y / \bar{y}_i^b$. In this way, a dimensionless evaluation indicator is obtained to measure mean square relative error.

4. CASE STUDY

The reference time horizon selected for the data analysis is one-year long and the time step chosen to discretize the continuous data is 1 hour, i.e. each parameter contains $N = 8760$ samples.

Sub-Blocks Parallelization. First, the parallelization of each block inputs and outputs is studied, with a threshold value on the EV equal to $\lambda_{\text{PCA}} = 5\%$. The study on the parallelization of those outputs and inputs not common to all the sub-blocks, showed a marked parallelization of both the blocks analyzed, with a resulting EV never lower than 10%. Consequently, to avoid an important loss of information, data analysis has been developed considering each sub-block as independent from the others, with $n_b = 4$ for purification and $n_b = 3$ for evaporation.

Modeling results. To establish the reliability of the predictive models, three thresholds are set up: *good* ($NRMSE_y \leq 0.10$), *adequate* ($0.10 < NRMSE_y \leq 0.30$), and *poor* ($NRMSE_y > 0.30$). Table 2a and Table 2b compare the prediction reliability of the PCR and PLS methods for the depuration and evaporation blocks. Although the PLS method usually has more effective predictions than the PCR method, the comparison by $NRMSE_y$ showed a non appreciable improvement for the two blocks. Results in Table 2a show a clear separation in the reliability of the prediction between the first two outputs (OUT1R and OUT2R) and the last three. The model reliability is good when predicting the pH values inside and at the top of the reactor but very poor when determining the concentrations of the main species inside the reactor. OUT5R is a qualitative measure given by the operator when visually judging the quality of the purified brine, hence its modeling is quite challenging. Table 2b shows both for the PCR and the PLS methods good reliability of the predictive models obtained with both regressive methods for the evaporative plant. The only output that appears to be worse than the others, but still showing discrete reliability (only 1.4% above the threshold value) is the OUT4EV1, that is the “ ΔT heat exchangers” for EV1. This may be due to the propagation of measurement errors derived from the fact that these values are taken as the difference between two measurements, weighing

Table 2. Prediction reliability of the two models calculated with PCR and PLS methods using $NRMSE_y$

	(a) Depuration block								(b) Evaporation block						
	PCR				PLS				PCR			PLS			
	R1	R2	R3	R4	R1	R2	R3	R4	EV1	EV2	EV3	EV1	EV2	EV3	
OUT1R	0.075	0.066	0.088	0.104	0.075	0.066	0.088	0.104	OUT1EV	0.044 (global parameter)			0.045 (global parameter)		
OUT2R	0.08	0.066	0.086	0.091	0.08	0.066	0.086	0.091	OUT2EV	0.023 (global parameter)			0.023 (global parameter)		
OUT3R	0.623	0.599	0.674	0.656	0.622	0.599	0.671	0.654	OUT3EV	0.023	0.003	0.005	0.023	0.003	0.005
OUT4R	0.494	0.420	0.551	0.490	0.493	0.420	0.552	0.491	OUT4EV	0.114	0.092	0.086	0.114	0.092	0.086
OUT5R	0.558	0.542	0.571	0.737	0.555	0.529	0.571	0.573							

on the NRMSE value. Generally, the use of automatic sensors and a monitoring system for the evaporation block leads to more frequent and reliable data. Conversely, in the depuration block, OUT2R, OUT3R, and OUT4R are quantified in laboratory tests for samples collected throughout the day.

Data variability and quality. To assess the performance of predictive models is also important to analyze the raw samples and the percentage of valid data for the regression. As shown in Table 1, the outputs considered are of different nature and thus the variability of the sample collected gives an a priori knowledge of which parameter can be difficult to fit. The results show how the standard deviation is relatively small for the outputs of the evaporation block, with a dataset that is therefore relatively stable. Vice versa, for the purification block, in particular for outputs OUT3R, OUT4R and OUT5R, the standard deviation is comparable to the arithmetic mean. This indicates highly variable data and consequently values that are difficult to correlate with the corresponding inputs. In addition, for an evaluation of the quality of the dataset collected, for each output, the percentage of data considered in the final models n_s compared to N raw data have been analyzed to evaluate the incidence of the screening performed as in Algorithm 1. Generally, for the evaporation block, the percentage of valid data is greater than 94% while for the depuration one this value is reached only by a few reactors (typically R2 and R3) and not for all the outputs.

5. CONCLUSION

The presented paper developed a predictive model through the analysis of historical data of the main parameters affecting the production process of brine salt in an Italian industrial site. This model focused on the analysis of purification and evaporation plants judged to be the most critical and of interest to control product quality. Production data was acquired via a direct connection to the plant DCS. The model was developed using PCR and PLS to identify the most significant and sensitive outputs with respect to changes in the plant operating conditions. The regression methods applied on a one-year long data range made it possible to conclude as follows regarding the reliability of the predictive models identified: the predictive model of the evaporation block was obtained with satisfactory reliability for almost all the considered outputs, while the one of the purification block showed very low reliability levels for three of the five quantities identified as output: impurities concentration in the reactors and the purified brine appearance. This is the starting point for taking more sophisticated modeling decisions: the predictive model of the depuration block can be improved by introducing custom delays between inputs and outputs; non-linear relations can be used to describe the reactor's behavior and the complex chemical equilibrium; a reduced dataset can also be tested to control data variability and model time periods that best represent nominal plant conditions. Also data cluster-

ing can be applied to improve the quality of the analyzed data. Finally, new inputs should be introduced if the previous options do not bring desired results.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by Sviluppato Regione Toscana through the POR CREO FESR 2014 - 2020 funding program (PROGETTO SE2030).

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